

THE WATERBENCHMARKHUB: A PLATFORM FOR BENCHMARKS IN WATER DISTRIBUTION NETWORKS

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ABSTRACT

Publicly accessible and user-friendly benchmarks are crucial for advancing and accelerating research in smart water systems and supporting reproducible studies. Benchmark resources related to Water Distribution Networks (WDNs) are difficult to access, as they are not consolidated within a centralized, standardized interface that could enhance their accessibility, usability, and relevance for researchers. Currently, they are dispersed across various sources, often poorly labelled and lacking clear guidance on their intended use or the research problems they address. In this work, we introduce the *WaterBenchmarkHub* platform, an open-source and community-driven platform, designed to offer a standardized interface for benchmarking resources. The *WaterBenchmarkHub* consists of a web interface for browsing the benchmark resources, and a Python package for easy access of those benchmark resources in Python. This project aims to enhance accessibility for a broader range of researchers and ultimately promote and strengthen reproducible research within the community.

Keywords: Benchmarks, Water Distribution Networks, Toolbox

INTRODUCTION

Water Distribution Networks (WDNs) are critical for ensuring a reliable supply of drinking water, traditionally managed through basic monitoring and control algorithms and limited sensor data. However, with urban population growth, these networks face increased complexity and time-varying uncertainties, complicating tasks like event detection, pump scheduling, and water quality modelling. Novel data-driven AI technologies offer the possibility to directly enhance traditional methods by the capability of reacting to challenges such as changing demands and system complexity. Modern data-driven (AI) approaches face unique challenges such as sparse sensor data and complex spatio-temporal signals. These circumstances often require novel AI models such as [1,2], which are often developed by non-water experts. Those non-water experts face several challenges including the lack of tools for straightforward scenario and data generation, as well as limited access to benchmarks, hindering the wider application of AI in the field.

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Figure 1. Web interface of the [WaterBenchmarkHub](#) platform.

studies. Benchmark resources related to Water Distribution Networks (WDNs) are difficult to access, as they are not consolidated within a centralized, standardized interface that could enhance their accessibility, usability, and relevance for researchers. Currently, they are dispersed across various sources, often poorly labelled and lacking clear guidance on their intended use or the research problems they address.

Existing databases and repositories containing water distribution network models, such as the Water Distribution System Research Database [3,9] or Exeter's Benchmark database [4] offer very promising avenues in this regard. However, they only contain a subset of all existing benchmarks without a standardized interface and have no clear update schedule or contribution guidelines on how to add new benchmark resources.

In this paper, we introduce the *WaterBenchmarkHub* platform, an open-source and community-driven platform, designed to offer a standardized interface for benchmarking resources. This initiative aims to enhance accessibility for a broader range of researchers and ultimately promote and strengthen reproducible research within the WDN community.

A PLATFORM FOR BENCHMARKS IN WATER DISTRIBUTION NETWORKS

The platform offers a curated collection of resources related to drinking water systems, including .INP files that define hydraulic models of water distribution networks, .MSX files that extend these models to simulate complex water quality dynamics and the behaviour of specific substances, benchmark scenarios such as BattLeDIM [5], control task environments, and various datasets. These models can be combined with simulated or real sensor data—as demonstrated in BattLeDIM—to create benchmarks tailored for research and

evaluation of methodologies in specific domains, such as leakage detection, localization, and control optimization. The platform goes beyond being a data repository, by providing algorithmic implementations of the evaluation metrics of the different benchmarks. Moreover, we release a Python package, to facilitate the easy access to all the benchmark resources within a programmatic environment. Additionally, it features an easy-to-use web platform that enables researchers to browse, search, and easily access these resources. Importantly, its open-source nature provides a user-friendly interface for contributing new resources, such as datasets and scenarios.

By offering publicly accessible, well-documented, and easy-to-use benchmarks, the WaterBenchmarkHub platform aims to facilitate and accelerate research in smart water systems, and to enhance reproducibility and comparability of newly developed methods and algorithms. Fig. 1 illustrates the web interface of the WaterBenchmarkHub platform.

Architecture of the Platform

The WaterBenchmarkHub platform is based on a database, which contains the meta-data of all included benchmark resources. These meta-data also include links to the actual data hosted on Zenodo, GitHub, or other platforms. The database of meta-data is implemented as a JSON file, accompanied by Markdown files containing an informative summary and description of the specific resources, which can be rendered in a web browser. Most importantly, included resources are also tagged with keywords and categorized to enhance its usability – those tags are included in the meta-data as well.

The entire database can be easily browsed and searched by an easy-to-use web interface, shown in Fig. 1.

In addition to the database, the WaterBenchmarkHub also comes with a Python package¹ for the easy access of all the benchmark resources in Python. The Python package not only allows to easily load resources such as data sets or .INP files but also provides implementations of the evaluation metrics of the different benchmarks. The Python package is compatible with EPyT-Flow [6] and can also be used with WNTR [7].

Below, an example on how to load the “GECCO Water Quality 2019” [8] benchmark data set:

```
from water_benchmark_hub import load

if __name__ == "__main__":
    # Load the GECCO Water Quality 2019 benchmark
    benchmark = load("GECCO-WaterQuality2019")

    # Load data set
    data = benchmark.load_data(return_X_y=True)

    # Show number of samples
    X_train, y_train = data["train"]
```

¹ <https://pypi.org/project/water-benchmark-hub/>

```
X_val, y_val = data["validation"]  
X_test, y_test = data["test"]  
print(X_train.shape, X_val.shape, X_test.shape)
```

Overview of the Benchmarks

As of today, the WaterBenchmarkHub includes 79 benchmark resources, covering the entire spectrum of research topics in water distribution networks. It includes 64 water distribution networks, described by .INP files, and 15 competition benchmarks with their associated scenario description and data, including all previous Battle Competitions from the water community. For those competition benchmarks, the WaterBenchmarkHub not only provides the data sets (or simulation environments) but also an implementation of the evaluation metrics.

How to contribute Benchmark Resources

The entire WaterBenchmarkHub platform is open-source and organized on GitHub² and is maintained by the community. Integrating new benchmarks into the WaterBenchmarkHub is done via Pull-requests and is kept as simple as possible. At a minimum, it requires adding a new entry of meta-data into the JSON database and adding a markdown file containing a human-readable description of the benchmark resource. If necessary, evaluation metrics or other supportive algorithmic logic can be implemented in Python and included in the Pull-request. The Pull-request is then reviewed by the community before it gets finally integrated into the database.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper introduced the WaterBenchmarkHub platform, an open-source and community-driven platform for collecting and providing benchmark resources regarding water distribution networks. The platform consists of a web interface for browsing the database, and a Python package for easy access of the benchmark resources in Python. Notably, the platform goes beyond being just a data repository but also provides detailed documentation of the benchmarks curated by the community and implementation of evaluation metrics for those specific benchmarks.

We will extend the collection and integrate upcoming benchmark resources and encourage the community to share and upload their resources, to promote and strengthen reproducible research within the WDN community.

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² <https://github.com/WaterFutures/WaterBenchmarkHub>

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